

The Paris Commune in Russian Historiography: Power, Mistakes and Damages According to the Ideas of Lenin and Skvortsov-Stepanov

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Abstract: After more than one hundred fifty years, the topic of the Paris Commune as a first example of a new form of government, even if it eventually proved to be fragile, is still worth scientific attention. The following work presents an outline of the moments that marked the beginning and the end of the Paris Commune, focusing on the impression perceived by V.I. Lenin and I. I. Skvortsov-Stepanov in Russian historiography about some of the structural characteristics and contradictions of this new politic and social phenomenon. The author starts from the political and economic background of France before the Franco-Prussian War, moving then on to the considerations of Lenin, as one of the most influent thinkers of pre-Soviet Russia, and Skvortsov-Stepanov, as one of the first Soviet scholars who investigated the causes and the damages suffered by Paris as an aftermath of the suppression of the Paris Commune. In the following work, the author illustrates a generous number of extracts in original language complete with professional translation.

Keywords: Paris Commune, Franco-Prussian War

Citation: Rubini, F. (2023). The Paris Commune in Russian Historiography: Power, Mistakes and Damages according to the Ideas of Lenin and Skvortsov-Stepanov. In W. Admiraal, E. Cakir, & M. L. Ciddi (Eds.), *Proceedings of ICHES 2023-- International Conference on Humanities, Education, and Social Sciences* (pp. 97-107), Amsterdam, Netherlands. ISTES Organization.

Introduction

In the second half of the XIX century, France, after having seen the strong influence of the events of the French Revolution and of the Napoleonic wars, had managed to survive repeated changes of forms of government, revolutions and other socio-political upheavals.

In fact, after 1814 there had been the Bourbon Restoration of Louis XVIII, even if briefly interrupted by Napoleon's return during the Hundred Days, then the reign of Charles X, the July Monarchy, the Second Republic, and the Second French Empire: six forms of government in a timespan of about forty years.

Strong in her political history, France also had had to cope with the activity of different new political parties, popular movements, different ruling élites and working class actions.

During the years of the Second French Empire, France had built one of the strongest economies in the world. By the end of the 1860s, with a level of relatively stable internal equilibrium and a strong colonial and political influence in the world, her GDP had doubled (Franck, 2014). During these years, France saw a great development of her railway network and trade, a growth of the popularity of her exports of colonial goods and the stunning architectural and urbanistic revolution of her capital.

Then, in 1870, after having failed to solve her political and strategic complaints towards the growing German influence in Spanish dynastic affairs, and in part deceived by Bismarck's cunning diplomatic ability, France found herself dragged into the Franco-Prussian War of 1870-1871, which eventually turned out to be a fatal mistake for France.

Strong in his confidence in his armed forces, Napoleon III declared war on Prussia on July 19, 1870 and appealed to his people soon afterwards with his famous proclamation on the 23rd of the same month. The last words of this document were (Bibliothèque nationale de France, n.d.):

“Dieu bénira nos efforts. Un grand peuple qui défend une cause juste est invincible.

Paris, le 23 juillet 1870”

“God will bless our efforts. A great people who defends a just cause is invincible.

Paris, July 23, 1870”

The Franco-Prussian War immediately proved to be a disaster for France: the French army was soundly defeated by unexpectedly overwhelming enemy forces in the major battles of Metz and especially Sedan, where the emperor himself was taken prisoner. Ashamed and humiliated by this series of defeats, French republicans dethroned Napoleon III, forming afterwards a popular form of government, and giving therefore birth in the capital of France to the period known as “the Paris Commune”.

This revolutionary government in Paris played a significant role for both French history itself and for the later history of socialist idea spreading throughout the world. Besides, it attracted the interest of many countries and intellectuals all around the world, which accurately followed the evolutions of the events at a distance.

The purpose of this work is to present an overview of how Russian historiography perceived this event, and how it wrote about it in the years that came after.

Method

The methods chosen for the following discussion are the historical comparative method, which permits us to compare two or more events, people, or cultures to analyze their similarities and differences; the interpretative method, which is necessary to present an interpretation of the meaning of past events, people, or cultures. Also, the quantitative and the qualitative methods of research are used, in order to present statistic data from historiographic sources and a discussion about their importance and possible interpretation.

Special attention deserves the translation method chosen in the work, in particular, the literary one; as we are about to see, the work required a wide use of professional, technical, and administrative translation as well, mostly because of the fact that the presented extracts have never been translated into Russian, or, in the case of Lenin's essays, for instance, even today they cannot always boast a 100% accurate translation.

Results

As social disasters in France worsened as a consequence of the Franco-Prussian War, economic stagnation not only persisted, but also took extreme forms, which caused famine among the population. The overspread devastation and decline were reinforced by the difficult foreign policy situation. The newly created National Guard, which was essentially a uniformed and armed mass of Parisians, found itself in an unfavorable position. The government that had capitulated to Prussia was preparing to disband the National Guard, starting from the cancelation of its wages. This and other measures led to the fact that on March 18, 1871, the National Guard organized an uprising, as a result of which, 8 days later, democratic elections were held for the Paris Commune.

The idea was to remove the conservative national assembly from command and elect the deputies of a new government at a parliamentary level, instead of a municipal one. So it was: during the Paris Commune, a wide range of measures were taken to abolish various social issues. For instance, rent arrears were abolished and bread prices were set. In addition to those measures, others were introduced to protect the rights of workers, night work in bakeries was prohibited, the remuneration policy in state bodies was changed, and privileged salaries were reduced.

The combination of the measures introduced by the Commune made it possible to abolish the old bureaucratic structure of the state. Having broken the old type of organization, the Commune built a new state, which was not yet familiar to history. This translated into the power of the working class, the first dictatorship of the proletariat, which was intended to carry the highest form of democracy: a (mostly) proletarian democracy. Election, responsibility, turnover, and collegiality were the democratic norms that formed the basis of the state apparatus of the Commune. The Commune abolished bourgeois parliamentarism, with the bourgeois principle of separation of powers (legislative, executive, judicial).

It is not hard to imagine that the study of the history of the Paris Commune, as well as its influence as a political and philosophical historical phenomenon, played a significant role in Russian historiography.

Discussion

Probably, the best known example is represented by Lenin's XIV tome of his "*sochinenija*" (*essays*). Here, among other things, he explores the cause-and-effect relationships of the formation of this phenomenon, as well as its very essence, and draws his conclusions about how the experience of the French can be assessed and analyzed in the context of the formation of a new state system in Russia.

In an article of the “Pravda” dated “April 9, 1917, N° 28” and entitled “*О двоевластии*” (“*about the dual power*”), Lenin identifies the three main characteristics of the power of the Commune (Lenin, 1925):

“1) Источник власти — не закон, предварительно обсужденный и проведенный парламентом, а прямой почин народных масс снизу и на местах, прямой «захват», употребляя ходячее выражение;

(The source of power is not a law previously discussed and enacted by parliament, but the direct initiative of the people from below, in their local areas, a direct “seizure”, to use a current expression;)

2) Замена полиции и армии, как отделенных от народа и противопоставленных народу учреждений прямым вооружением всего народа; государственный порядок при такой власти охраняют сами вооруженные рабочие и крестьяне, сам вооруженный народ;

(The replacement of the police and the army, which are institutions separated from the people and set against the people, by the direct arming of the whole people; public order in a state under such a power is maintained by the armed workers and peasants themselves, by the armed people themselves;)

3) Чиновничество, бюрократия либо заменяются опять-таки непосредственной властью самого народа, либо по меньшей мере ставятся под особый контроль, превращаются не только в выборных, но и в сменяемых по первому требованию народа, сводятся на положение простых уполномоченных; из привилегированного слоя с высокой, буржуазной оплатой «местечек» превращаются в рабочих особого «рода оружия», оплачиваемых не выше обычной платы хорошего рабочего.”

(Officialdom and bureaucracy are either similarly replaced by the direct rule of the people themselves or at least placed under special control; they not only become elected officials, but also replaceable at the people’s first demand; they are reduced to the position of simple delegates; from a privileged class of “nice jobs” with a high and bourgeois remuneration, they turn into workers of a special “armed force”, whose remuneration does not exceed the ordinary pay of a good worker.)

According to Lenin’s idea, in this, and only in this, was the essence of the Commune. Beside this, Lenin’s aim was to formulate a fundament, basing himself on the philosophy of Marx and Engels, able to contribute to the development of this relatively new historiographic trend in the Russian-speaking research environment. This new trend was quite understandable, as the beginning of the XX century was already being characterized by revolutions, struggles between the proletariat and capitalism etc. For this reason, the importance of the Paris Commune as a phenomenon was especially exalted during the formation of a new state with new rules and postulates, as that had been the only massive event of that kind which attracted the attention of the whole world. Therefore, in his works Lenin pointed out the focal moments in the formation of the Commune, including its universality, its readiness to accept and take into account various opinions, and democracy. In addition, he

identified various reasons for the eventual failure in the formation of this phenomenon, namely a weak position in relation to the opponents of the new form.

«Две ошибки погубили плоды блестящей победы. Пролетариат остановился на полпути: вместо того, чтобы приступить к «экспроприации экспроприаторов», он увлекся мечтами о водворении высшей справедливости в стране, объединяемой общенациональной задачей; такие, например, учреждения, как банк, не были взяты, теории прудонистов насчет «справедливого обмена» и т. п. господствовали еще среди социалистов. Вторая ошибка — излишнее великодушие пролетариата: надо было истреблять своих врагов, а он старался морально повлиять на них, он пренебрег значением чисто военных действий в гражданской войне и вместо того, чтобы решительным наступлением на Версаль увенчать свою победу в Париже, он медлил и дал время версальскому правительству собрать темные силы и подготовиться к кровавой майской неделе»

(Two mistakes ruined the fruits of a brilliant victory. The proletariat stopped halfway: instead of proceeding to the "expropriation of the expropriators," it revealed distracted by the dream of establishing a supreme justice in a country united by a national mission; institutions like banks, for instance, were not taken: the Proudhonist theories about "fair exchange" etc. were still dominant among the socialists. The second mistake was the excessive generosity of the proletariat: it was supposed to exterminate its enemies, while it tried to influence them morally; it ignored the importance of purely military actions in the civil war, instead of crowning his victory in Paris with a decisive attack on Versailles, it hesitated and gave the government of Versailles the time to gather dark forces and get prepared for the "semaine sanglante".)

Before moving on to the point of view of the next scholar, we think the following image (see Figure 1) is worth consideration: this is the introductory slide of a famous 1976 Soviet filmstrip about the Paris Commune (see "Recommendations").

Figure 1

As we can see, it shows the title, of course, and a quote from Lenin. More precisely (including the dots):

“...Коммуна боролась...за освобождение всего трудящегося человечества, всех униженных и оскорбленных. ...Дело Коммуны...до сих пор живет в каждом из нас.”

(“The Commune fought...for the liberation of all working mankind, of all the humiliated and insulted. ...The cause of the Commune...still lives in every one of us.”)

The meaning of these words does not need particular interpretation or explanation. Nevertheless, it deserves to be underlined that, in the quote, Lenin uses the expression “*humiliated and insulted*” (*униженные и оскорбленные*), which in our opinion is a clear allusion to Dostoevskij’s famous work. The author, in fact, already in the 1860s had tried to condemn the dark sides of capitalism in Russia, depicting the defenseless existence of miserable people against the cynicism of the rich.

Analyzing the position of the Paris Commune in Russian historiography, Skvortsov-Stepanov deserves attention as well, as he was one of the first Soviet scholars who studied the issue of the formation of this phenomenon. In his work “*The Paris Commune of 1871 and Questions of Tactics of the Proletarian Revolution*”, the author aimed to draw the main conclusions about this phenomenon as a whole. Besides, although this work is not initially a deep study of causal relationships, it remains important in the context of studying the stages of formation and fall of the Paris Commune (Skvortsov-Stepanov, 1937).

In our opinion, particular attention deserves the author’s well-argued and very precise consideration about the impressive damages, in terms of both lost work force and human lives, which Paris suffered as a result of the suppression of the Commune:

“Некоторым отраслям парижской промышленности был нанесен жестокий удар истреблением работников. Генерал Анпер в отчете следственной комиссии о 18-м марта дал такие сведения о профессии осужденных: литераторы 2.901, слесари и механики 2.664, каменщики 2.293, столяры 1.659, торговые служащие 1.598, сапожники 1.491, служащие 1.065, маляры 863, типографские рабочие 819, каменотесы 766, портные 681, столяры-полировщики 636, ювелиры 528, плотники 382, кожевники 347, скульпторы 283, жестяники 227, литейщики 224, шапочники 210, портнихи 206, басонщики 193, часовых дел мастера 179, позолотчики 172, печатники обоев 159, формовщики 157, картонажники 124, переплетчики 106, преподаватели 106 и т. д.”

(“Some branches of Parisian industry suffered a severe blow by the extermination of the workers. General Appert, in the report to the investigation committee about March 18, gave the following information about the profession of the convicts: writers 2,901, locksmiths and mechanics 2,664, masons 2,293, carpenters 1,659, trade employees 1,598, shoemakers 1,491, employees 1,065, decorators 863, printing workers 819, stonecutters 766, tailors 681, planer operators 636, goldsmiths 528, carpenters 382, leather workers 347, sculptors 283,

tinsmiths 227, casters 224, hat makers 210, dressmakers 206, cutters 193, watchmakers 179, gilders 172, wallpaper manufacturers 159, moulders 157, cartoners 124, bookbinders 106, teachers 106, etc.”)

And again:

“К осени 1871 года новый парижский муниципалитет предпринял обследование парижской промышленности и торговли и получил следующие данные: в сапожном производстве до 18-го марта было занято 24.000 рабочих, оно потеряло 12.000, т.-е. как раз половину, убитыми, арестованными и эмигрировавшими; в производстве готового платья убыль рабочих составила 5.000 человек, в мебельном производстве предместья Сент-Антуан — 6.000, в малярном производстве пришлось заменить мастеров учениками; убыль кровельщиков, жестяников и т. д. составила 3.000 человек; сильно пострадали все отрасли производства так называемых «парижских изделий» [...]”

“By the autumn of 1871, the new Parisian municipality undertook a survey of Parisian industry and trade and received the following information: in the shoe industry of the city were employed 24,000 workers until March 18. It lost 12,000 of them, that is, exactly half, all killed, arrested and emigrated. In the production of ready-made dresses, the loss of workers amounted to 5,000 people, in the furniture production of the suburb of Saint-Antoine 6,000, in the painting industry, the masters had to be replaced by apprentices; the loss of roofers, tinsmiths, etc. amounted to 3,000 people; every sector of production of the so-called "Parisian products", suffered greatly [...]”

And again:

“В самых беспощадных национальных войнах побежденному врагу дается пощада. Никакой пощады не знает буржуазия по отношению к восставшему и побежденному пролетариату. Это показал конец Парижской Коммуны, — это показали расправы контрреволюции после русской революции 1905 года, это много раз показало временное торжество контрреволюции в некоторых областях современной России.”

“In the most merciless national wars, mercy is given to the defeated enemy. The bourgeoisie knows no mercy towards the insurgent and defeated proletariat. This was shown by the end of the Paris Commune: this was shown by the reprisals of the counter-revolution after the Russian Revolution of 1905, this was shown many times by the temporary triumph of the counter-revolution in certain regions of today's Russia”

Russian historiography of the Paris Commune did actually prove able to offer a great contribution to its philosophical and scientific study; many of the most brilliant minds of the time of all scientific spheres worked on it. However, we should keep in mind that actually it was unprofitable for Soviet historiography, with its obvious guidelines, to speak and highlight the real problems within French society; the key passage to be understood in this regard is that scholars presented them as mistakes, rather than serious social problems with short-term and long-term consequences.

For instance, in Soviet sciences it was generally explained that one of the reasons why other cities in France did not support the capital was actually the irresponsibility of citizens or their unpreparedness for transformations. The solving of real problems, food shortages etc. was of secondary importance for obvious reasons. The political situation and, consequently, the impossibility to talk about the problems of the system represented a kind of sword of Damocles for historians.

Of course, speaking about Soviet historiography, we understand the extremely positive and high assessment of such a phenomenon as the Paris Commune. This is quite understandable, because to some extent it represented *de facto* a first project of dictatorship of the proletariat, a *topos* that was perceived with great excitement in all aspects of Soviet society.

The weak communication between the Commune and the country, the underestimated importance of the military and strategic situation, and the powerful and active support offered by Germany led to the blockade of the Paris Commune inside its own capital, which eventually culminated in a merciless and bloody eight-day massacre inside the city. Therefore, on May 28, 1871, after having existed for 72 days, the Paris Commune collapsed, having lost a huge number of prominent figures of its movement and civilians.

The formation of the Commune became for many a symbol of the beginning of a new era, an era of a new and to some extent experimental state policy. It represented a new model for the political structure of a single democratic republic. In practice, the Paris Commune, while maintaining a bureaucratic component, as well as some authoritarian features, began to implement the ideas of a welfare state.

This complex historical phenomenon existed only for a few months; few months during which some people saw the end of the French bourgeois revolution of the XVIII century, while others believed in the revival of medieval communes. In fact, this was the realization of a new type of state, the first world experience of proletarian dictatorship characterized by elections, an idea of responsibility, and turnover as the main features of a democratic form of government.

Conclusion

In Russia, the phenomenon represented by the Paris Commune became a subject of heated controversy between anarchists and Marxists, and about which Soviet scholars developed thousands of analyses and theories. In general, it was considered erroneous to believe that the only goal of the Commune was to ensure local self-government through the means of armed rebellions; this was, first of all, the first experience of dictatorship of the proletariat, which became an important example and an exciting first record in history for the socialist movement as a whole.

In Paris there is a famous cemetery, the cemetery of Père-Lachaise, in which today visitors can see a commemorative plaque on a wall that is called “the Communards’ Wall” (in French: “*le Mur des Fédérés*”). Here Parisians and visitors bring flowers to remember the soldiers and the officers who were executed during the last day of the *Seimane Sanglante* and buried in a common grave at the foot of the wall. This tablet is one of the very few commemorative symbols left for posterity in France.

What about Russia? Actually, today in Russia we can still see a few signs of the homage paid by the previous generations to the historical memory of this event. For instance, in the district of Bor, in Nizhnyj Novgorod Region, there is a settlement whose name is “*Pamjat’ Parizhskoj Kommuny*” (Память Парижской Коммуны), which literally means “*The memory of the Paris Commune*” (see Figure 2).

Figure 2

This village was originally founded in 1869 with the name of “*Zhukovskij Zaton*” (Жуковский Затон), then it was renamed with its current name (see Figure 2). Another interesting example of memorial we can see today is that dedicated to the Paris Commune in the city of Omsk (see Figure 3 and Figure 4).

Figure 3

Figure 4

The very creation of this memorial is still today object of debate: one thesis argues that it was originally thought to commemorate the victims of the massacres perpetrated by the White Army which took place in 1919, just before the seizing of the city by the 3rd and the 5th Red Armies. The project was ready in March 1920, but it was soon afterwards suspended because of a shortage of funds. What we do know is that in March 1921, on the eve of the 50th anniversary of the Paris Commune, next to the Drama Theater was erected this monument in memory of the fallen communards. The author was Nikolaj Vinogradov, who afterwards proposed to move it to the spot where the victims of the Whites had been buried; the opening ceremony took place in July 1923 (Naumov, 2017).

Leaving aside the political background of the events which led to the construction of this monument and moving on to its description, we can see a man and a woman, both dressed in a way that resembles the simple workers of the time, and a banner. The man, wounded and with his right arm touching his chest, is falling backwards, while the woman is supporting his body with her left arm and is raising the banner with the right one. The scene is dynamic and swift, an impression that is suggested by the contrast between the movement of the man in one direction and that of the woman in the other; a sensation of continuity. On the banner we can see the inscription “C.C.C.P.” (USSR), which aims to underline another kind of continuity: the continuity of the deeds of past generations through time.

About the tablets on the pedestal of the sculpture, they were changed many times in the years, but one of them stated:

“Коммунары Парижа! У вас вырвали Красное Знамя, рабочие России отняли его и победили!”

(Communards of Paris! The Red Banner had been snatched from your hands, the workers of Russia took it away and won!)

Recommendations

For a deeper and clearer understanding of the importance of the Paris Commune for Russian history, and to get acquainted with a huge selection of materials, many of which translated into Russian, we strongly recommend to visit the dedicated section offered by the project called “*Исторические материалы*” (Proekt “Istoricheskie Materialy”, (n.d.)). Another great source that is worth mentioning is the content of the famous filmstrip about the Paris Commune commissioned by the Ministry of Education of USSR in 1976 for ninth-grade pupils (Diafilm Parizhskaia Kommuna, (n.d.)): a very fine source of vignettes and illustrations that gives us a clear look of the Soviet perception of the topic and of its presentation for the masses.

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